

**MAPPING CORPORATE HARM TO HUMAN RIGHTS AND THE ENVIRONMENT:
THE BRAVE DATABASE**

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Abstract

Mapping and measuring corporate harm to human rights and the environment remains difficult due to limited data transparency and inconsistent reporting standards. Yet robust information is essential to understand the magnitude of the problem, track progress, and support an empirical research agenda capable of identifying what effectively curbs business-related misconduct and related questions. This paper introduces a new open-access dataset documenting alleged human rights and environmental abuses – the REBALANCE Business-related Human Rights and Environmental (BRAVE) database - involving 83 of the largest publicly listed European multinational corporations between 2000 and 2020. Built from systematic data collection from the Business & Human Rights Resource Centre, the dataset codes allegations by type of abuse, country, victims affected, corporate involvement (direct or indirect), and severity, enabling both comparative and longitudinal analyses. 98 per cent of the monitored firms are associated with at least one alleged abuse. This pattern suggests that such incidents are common rather than isolated. By offering a transparent and replicable empirical foundation, BRAVE aims at supporting evidence-based research, policy development, and stronger corporate accountability in the business and human rights field.

Keywords: Human rights and environmental abuses; Corporate accountability; European multinational corporations; Business and human rights; Measuring corporate harm

Attribution of the Dataset, Disclaimers and Contacts: The BRAVE dataset can be downloaded from here: <https://rebalanceproject.org/data/>. Users of the dataset are requested to cite this article as the primary reference. While every effort has been made to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data, the database may contain omissions or errors. The coders have relied on available secondary sources to verify reported information to the best of their ability. As noted, the dataset codifies reported allegations of human rights and/or environmental abuses. Researchers seeking further information are invited to contact: rebalanceprojecteu@gmail.com.

INTRODUCTION

Research at the intersection of business and human rights (BHR) has long examined the diverse ways in which firms may contribute—directly or indirectly—to human rights harm. Foundational work in this field has documented corporate involvement in abuses ranging from labor rights abuses to severe environmental harm affecting the rights of individuals and communities (Giuliani and Macchi 2014; Wettstein 2012). While an extensive body of scholarship has explored the determinants of corporate misconduct, including organizational incentives, governance failures, and pressures within global value chains (Olsen 2023; Vogel 2005), other research has focused on the consequences of such misconduct for affected rightsholders, local communities, and firms themselves, including impacts on profitability, legitimacy, and long-term competitiveness (Nieri and Giuliani 2018; Henisz, Dorobantu, and Nartey 2014).

Parallel to these empirical inquiries, scholars have also traced the substantial normative developments that have transformed the BHR landscape over the past two decades. From the Draft Norms on the Responsibilities of Transnational Corporations and Other Business Enterprises with Regard to Human Rights (Draft Norms) in the early 2000s, to the endorsement of the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) in 2011, to the ongoing emergence of mandatory human rights and environmental due diligence legislation in multiple jurisdictions, the field has witnessed a marked institutionalization of human rights expectations vis-à-vis business (Ruggie 2013; Deva and Birchall 2020). At the corporate level, human rights language has progressively permeated sustainability reports, codes of conduct, and voluntary commitments, with firms increasingly pledging to respect human rights across their operations and supply chains (Corciolani et al. 2024; Buhmann 2017).

Despite these advances, however, several fundamental questions remain unresolved—questions that lie at the core of BHR scholarship. Most notably: to what extent are these normative developments driving actual changes in corporate behavior? Are firms substantively improving their human rights performance, or are commitments largely symbolic? Do soft-law instruments such as

the UNGPs exert meaningful influence, or is hard-law regulation more effective in reducing human rights misconduct? And which firms are more likely to respond to these normative pressures? Addressing what some scholars have termed the “effectiveness gap” (Nolan and Taylor 2009; Backer 2020) requires robust, longitudinal, firm-level evidence on corporate involvement in human rights abuses.

A small number of recent projects have begun to engage in these questions empirically. For example, Giuliani, Nieri and colleagues (2017; 2023) have developed longitudinal datasets of corporate human rights controversies to investigate the drivers of human rights misconduct. Also, using a longitudinal dataset – the Corporations and Human Rights Database - focusing on Latin America, Olsen and colleagues (2023; 2022) have examined institutional determinants of firms’ human rights misconduct. Yet such efforts rely on proprietary or hand-coded data, limiting transparency, replicability, and access for the broader scholarly community. Other researchers have used ESG (environmental, social, governance) indicators as proxies for human rights performance (Rathert 2016; Cuervo-Cazurra, Purkayastha, and Ramaswamy 2023); however, there is now strong evidence that ESG metrics are not well-suited for capturing human rights harm, mostly due to misconceptions of human rights in ESG communities – which often equate the “S” with human rights, while human rights infringements may well occur in connection with environmental (E) and governance (G) areas, let alone other biases and measurement errors of these metrics as highlighted in earlier research (Berg, Kölbel, and Rigobon 2022; Chatterji et al. 2016).

To advance empirical work in the BHR field, we propose that the scholarly community requires openly available, systematically coded, firm-level data on corporate involvement in human rights misconduct. Importantly, we consider environmental harm within the scope of human rights because environmental degradation directly affects the enjoyment of fundamental rights, including the rights to life, health, water, food, and an adequate standard of living. To address this fundamental data gap, we developed a new open-access database that longitudinally records allegations of

corporate human rights abuses and environmental harm: the REBALANCE Business-related Human Rights and Environmental database (hereinafter BRAVE).

This article serves as the primary reference for the BRAVE dataset. We detail its construction, coding methodology, scope, and key characteristics, and outline how it can be combined with additional firm-level or institutional datasets to support diverse research agendas. By providing open access, interoperable data on reported business-related human rights and environmental abusive events, we aim to contribute to a more evidence-based assessment of whether—and under what conditions—normative developments in the BHR field translate into concrete improvements for rightsholders.

THE REBALANCE BUSINESS-RELATED HUMAN RIGHTS AND ENVIRONMENTAL DATABASE (BRAVE)

Scope and Selection of Monitored Firms

Given the scope of the project, we restricted our work to a subset of European multinational firms. In defining the set of monitored firms, we followed established research practice (e.g., Marano, Tashman, and Kostova 2017) by selecting the largest publicly listed European¹ companies featured in at least one edition of UNCTAD’s annual list of the top 100 non-financial companies by foreign assets between 2010 and 2020. This list is published annually in the World Investment Report (WIR), one of UNCTAD’s flagship publications on global foreign direct investment trends.

The final sample comprises 83 multinational corporations. Table 1 provides a breakdown by companies’ home country. As expected, the distribution reflects both the relative size of the European economies and their degree of internationalization. Specifically, nearly 70% of the companies originate from France (24%), the UK (24%), Germany (16%), and Switzerland (7%). Other significant contributors include Italy, Ireland, and the Netherlands, each accounting for roughly 5%

¹ We considered the countries listed in the EU27, as well as the United Kingdom, Norway, and Switzerland.

of the sample. Our sample covers firms in the extractive (18%), chemicals and pharmaceuticals (14%), electricity (12%), food, beverage, and tobacco (11%), telecommunications (10%), and 36% across automotive, electronics, retail, healthcare, ICT, real estate, transport, textiles, and consumer goods.

TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE

Codification Procedure

To construct the database, we employed a systematic and transparent procedure for gathering, validating, and coding reported business-related human rights and environmental abuses (hereinafter, *abuses*). It is important to underscore that our contribution lies in codifying discrete abusive events that have been reported as being associated with the monitored firms. These reported abuses should be understood as allegations. We use the term allegation to refer to a claim that a company has caused an adverse impact on human rights and/or the environment in the course of its business activities, or has contributed to such an impact through its involvement in a global value chain or another third-party actor.

We manually systematized the reported abusive events using the universe of qualitative materials (news, reports, videos, memos, etc.) gathered over the years and provided to us by the Business & Human Rights Resource Centre (BHRRC) — a widely recognized and credible knowledge hub in this field (Bernaz 2016; Ruggie 2013; Olsen 2023; van den Herik and Letnar Cernic 2010). More specifically, the BHRRC systematically collects and curates reports of business-related human rights and environmental abuses, ensuring the exclusion of unfounded or unverifiable claims. Since the BHRRC has been operational since 2000, our dataset covers the entire 2000–2020 period. The data collection, conducted between June 2023 and June 2025, was intentionally limited to allegations up to 2020 to account for the observed average three-year lag between the occurrence of an abuse and its public reporting — a pattern consistent with prior research (Giuliani, Nieri, and Vezzulli 2023). We collaborated directly with analysts at the BHRRC to access their comprehensive

archive of documents related to the firms in our sample —see next section. The codification process was extensive. It involved a dedicated team of five researchers and over 50 research assistants engaged in both systematization and cross-validation processes.²

Our team reviewed over 27,000 documents, including CSO/NGO reports, news articles, journal publications, and even video documentaries. While most materials were in English, we employed translators for documents in other languages when necessary. For each document, we first assessed whether it included an allegation of human rights and/or environmental abuse involving any of the monitored companies. When such an allegation was identified, we systematically coded it to record a set of relevant information, ensuring consistency and comparability across sources.

Importantly, codification has followed a protocol that has been developed after dedicated consultations and focus groups with different human rights experts and stakeholders.³ In the codification process, we exclude incidents likely not attributable to firm-level decision-making. For instance, abuses involving workers' misbehavior for personal reasons or accidents resulting purely from individual negligence or natural disasters were omitted. However, incidents suggesting corporate neglect—such as failures in plant maintenance leading to harm—were included. Each codified abusive event captures a distinct type of human rights and/or environmental abuse involving the monitored company. For instance, if in year t a firm is reported for abusing labor rights at one of its plants in Nicaragua, and in the same year there is evidence of the same type of abuse in Honduras, we coded two separate events as these are two separate instance of the same type abuse perpetrated

² To ensure inter-coder reliability, we followed prior research (Lombard, Snyder-Duch, and Bracken 2002; Nardella, Surdu, and Brammer 2023) by starting the coding process with a pilot test based on a sample of 200 human rights and environmental abuses drawn from 700 documents. All coders examined the documents. We refined the pro-forma and coding instructions until the informal, pilot study suggested an adequate level of agreement, namely over 90% (e.g., agreement about the typology in which an event would be placed, the most appropriate geographic location, the years when it occurred, the type of company involvement, how to manage events which re-emerge in subsequent years, etc.). Next, we formally assessed reliability using the percent agreement technique based on a sample of 500 human rights and environmental abuses; inter-coder agreement was high, as coders agreed on their coding results over 95% of instances.

³ The project's team and external experts met in March 2023 to discuss the codification protocol starting from the qualitative corpus provided by the BHRRC. It was agreed to construct an open-access, firm-level database, starting from the BHRRC's taxonomy of abuses and victims and refining it based on prior art and subsequent focus groups with experts. It was decided to rely on BHRRC's secondary material and other secondary sources, while no primary data collection was undertaken for this project.

in two different places. Similarly, if in year t a firm is reported for violating consumers' right to health and, in the same year, evidence also indicates that the firm exploited workers at one of its plants, we codified two separate events involving the same firm. This allows us to capture distinct forms of misconduct that may occur concurrently and to maintain analytical granularity in our dataset. To avoid duplication, we ensured that identical allegations reported across multiple sources were coded only once per company involved.

Codification of Reported Abuses

In the next subsections, we detail the information coded in the BRAVE dataset for each identified human rights and/or environmental abuse. We note that the first release of the database is under the name BRAVE_v0.

General information. We first documented a set of general information to help qualify for the abusive event. Specifically, we assigned a unique code to each abuse reported by our data sources (*Abuse ID* in the BRAVE_v0 database), identified the company involved (*Company ID* and *Company name*), and provided a brief description of the abuse (*Brief description*) for example, “company’s gas flaring practices in Nigeria’s Niger Delta contribute to severe health problems like respiratory illnesses, asthma, and cancer among local communities”. We also recorded the country where the abuse has allegedly occurred (*Country*) and the year(s) during which the abuse has been reported to have occurred, including the year in which the abuse is known to have started (*Year of alleged start*)—and the year in which it is considered to have ceased (*Year of alleged end*). Additionally, we noted the year in which the abuse was first reported by the considered source or denounced (*Year first reported*), and whether it was part of a legal case brought against the company (*Legal vs reported*). Finally, we specified the type of source from which the information used to codify the abuse was first reported by the BHRRC or other secondary sources (i.e., academic and research; company; CSO; government; independent oversight body; intergovernmental organization; legal; media) (*Type of source*).

Type of abuse. We classified human rights and/or environmental abuses into 19 macro-categories (*Type* in the BRAVE_v0 database), each comprising several subtypes (*Subtype* in the BRAVE_v0 database). *Type* encompasses abuses of individual, collective, and labor rights, as well as harms associated with environmental degradation, public health issues, and governance failures. These typologies have emerged through bottom-up coding, and each corresponds to a class of human rights, as defined by international human rights law. The first group of abuses of fundamental human rights encompasses practices that violate the dignity, integrity, and freedom of individuals. These include *child labor* (1), which undermines children’s development and well-being and remains widespread in global supply chains, including those linked to the energy transition (ILO 1973; 1999); and *slavery* (2) observed through evidence of forced labor, debt bondage, and coercive recruitment practices (ILO 1930), often hidden within complex and opaque supply chains (Crane 2013; Crane et al. 2022). *Torture* (3) is another typology we have observed which refers to severe physical and psychological abuses perpetrated in collusion with state or private security forces, in violation of jus cogens norms of international law (United Nations 1984). Likewise, we observed cases of (4) *human trafficking* - defined as the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring, or receipt of persons for the purpose of exploitation through coercion or abuse of vulnerability—and other illicit commercial practices (United Nations 2000). While not always involving direct human exploitation, such practices may nonetheless implicate companies in human rights and environmental abuses, such as in Nestlé’s case in Guatemala, where palm oil estates were reportedly used by drug trafficking networks to operate (Reuters, 2019).

Among the most notable human rights violations identified in the codification we observed (5) *deprivation of life* (various forms of killings) and (6) *violence and harassment* – encompassing abductions, sexual violence, violent repression of protest and fatal workplace incidents. Both these typologies of abuses disproportionately affect communities opposing large-scale projects, revealing a structural link between social conflict, power imbalances, and inadequate protective measures (United Nations 1966). We also identified different forms of *discrimination* (7), defined as a cross-

cutting category, emerging on the basis of gender, pregnancy, medical status, racial or ethnic origin, caste, religion or belief, and sexual orientation, reflecting entrenched structural inequalities (United Nations 1966).

Next, *labor rights abuses* (8) constitute another typology that include the denial of leave entitlements – such as sick, maternity and annual leave - which undermines workers’ physical and mental well-being; the systematic use of precarious forms of employment (e.g., temporary, subcontracted, or casual contract) depriving workers of job security and long-term social protections. Moreover, unjust dismissals, particularly of workers who attempt to organize or report abuses, remain a common tactic to suppress dissent and collective action; informal or undocumented work arrangements which expose workers to vulnerability, as they frequently fall outside the scope of legal protections and labor inspections. Other forms of labor exploitation are excessive or unpaid overtime, abuses of occupational health and safety standards (e.g., lack of protective equipment, training, or emergency procedures), and the imposition of recruitment fees, especially in the case of migrant workers (ILO 1981). Wage-related abuses also fall in this group – including underpayment, withholding of wages, or failure to comply with legal entitlements – are among the most frequently reported, undermining the rights to fair remuneration as recognized under Article 7 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ILO 1973; United Nations 1966).

Companies’ *negative environmental impacts* (9) are also extensively documented, often interlinked. These include air, water, and soil pollution, climate change, loss of biodiversity, and abuses of environmental safety standards, frequently tied to unsustainable resource extraction. Impacts affect not only protected ecosystems but also communities whose access to basic resources is undermined. The precautionary principle, articulated in Article 191(2) of the Treaty on Foundation of European Union (European Union 2012), imposes a duty on states—and by extension on corporations—to prevent environmental and health harms, even under scientific uncertainty. The UNGPs similarly affirm corporate responsibility to respect environmental and health standards.

The next set of abuse (10), *negative health impacts*, is a macro-category that includes harms to physical and mental health arising from business activities, such as exposure to pollution, loss of livelihoods, poor living conditions, and restricted access to food, water, or medicine. Unsafe consumer products further illustrate corporate neglect of health and safety obligations, undermining the right to health and adequate standard of living (United Nations 1966; 2011).

Another typology included in the dataset is *negative impacts on heritage* (11), which includes business activities or practices that destroy, appropriate, or undermine tangible and intangible cultural heritage, thus eroding collective identity, spiritual traditions, and intergenerational ties to land and history (United Nations 1966; United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization 2003).

Displacement (12) is another harm observed when businesses, especially in infrastructure and extractive sectors, have been linked to the forced removal of communities without meaningful consultation, adequate compensation, or resettlement measures (United Nations Economic and Social Council 1998).

Next, governance and security-related abuses capture corporate involvement in practices that erode democratic institutions or facilitate unlawful conduct. *Corruption* (13) and *complicity* (14) with state or paramilitary forces capture situations where businesses contribute to or benefit from unlawful practices that erode democratic institutions (UNGA, 2003; OECD 2023). Other documented categories include *production and trade of weapons of mass destruction* (15), which directly contravene international peace and security obligations (United Nations 2013), and *tax avoidance and evasion*, (16), which, while often formally legal, undermine states' ability to fulfill their human rights obligations by eroding fiscal capacity (OECD 2012) – and some scholars may want to include this typology among the human rights harms.

Abuses targeting civic and political rights include intimidation, restriction, and abusive legal action. Among them, *intimidation* (17) covers practices aimed at silencing or coercing individuals and communities who challenge corporate conduct or defend human rights. Documented abuses

encompass death threats against activists, workers, or community leaders; surveillance and monitoring of union activities, journalists, or CSOs; and other forms of harassment or pressure designed to suppress dissent (United Nations General Assembly 1998). The typology (18) *restriction* covers corporate actions that unlawfully limit fundamental civil and political rights. These include arbitrary arrest or detentions of workers, trade unionists, community leaders, and human rights defenders; infringements of privacy through surveillance or data misuse; and restrictions on freedom of association and expression, often targeting unions, journalists, and activists. Such measures violate core international standards protecting participation, dissent, and collective organization (United Nations 1966; ILO 1948). The dataset also includes the category of (19) *abusive legal action*, which refers to the strategic use of legal systems to intimidate, silence, or burden individuals and organizations that expose corporate misconduct or defend human rights. Such practice is known as Strategic Lawsuits against Public Participation (SLAPPs) and other vexatious claims filed against journalists, researchers, trade unionists, or activists, with the aim of deterring scrutiny through financial pressure, reputational harm, or protracted litigation. By exploiting legal frameworks for retaliatory purposes, corporations and their affiliates undermine access to justice and the rights to freedom of expression and participation in public affairs (European Union 2024).

Appendix A provides a detailed description of the specific abuses encompassed within each category.

Type of victims. We identified the victims impacted by the abuse (*Type of victims* in the BRAVE_v0 database), grouped in the five macro categories of (1) *children*, (2) *workers and trade unionists*, (3) *communities*, (4) *consumers and clients*, and (5) *activists and journalists*.

Children (1) emerge as a distinct category, due to the heightened protection they enjoy under international law, including the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, which recognized their special vulnerability and the obligation to prioritize their best interest (United Nations General Assembly 1989). The cases show children as victims of situations that expose them to profound physical, developmental and psychological harm – from exploitative conditions, child labor practices

and coercive environments to health-damaging contexts created by toxic exposure, unsafe products, unethical medical practices, and environmental degradation – often resulting in lasting harms or death. *Workers and trade unionists* (2) constitute another broad group of victims, frequently affected by unequal power relations within workplaces and across supply chains. Discrimination also emerges, as in the case of dismissal based on ethnic origin, gender, and sexual orientation. Other examples include mass layoffs and involuntary transfers, or retaliatory legal actions against protesting workers. In several instances, workers have suffered serious health consequences, such as long-term exposure to toxic chemicals. The situation worsens in global supply chains, where reports of forced labor, torture, and trafficking illustrate how abusive is often concealed behind layers of subcontracting. Even more routine abuses, such as corporate bans on speaking on the assembly line, reflect the dehumanizing effects of certain production models.

Communities (3), especially those living near extractive or infrastructural projects, are also disproportionately affected by corporate operations. These impacts can include mass displacement, environmental destruction, significant threats to health and livelihoods, as well as the loss or degradation of cultural and archaeological heritage. In some cases, communities report harassment and heightened security measures, raising concerns about possible collusion between private and state. Opposition to harmful projects often leads to intimidation and criminalization of local community activists.

The dataset also includes corporate *consumers and clients* (4), victims primarily through exposure to unsafe products and misleading marketing practices. In several cases, companies failed to adequately inform or protect end-users, resulting in serious health consequences. Among the most notable cases, there is that of Bayer's pesticide which was misperceived as a fertilizer in Brazil, leading to mass poisonings and at least 30 deaths among coffee growers due to improper use and inadequate safety warnings (Duarte Reyes 2024). Similarly, major car manufacturers, including BMW, faced lawsuits in the United States for allegedly concealing the dangers of carbon monoxide poisoning in vehicles with keyless ignition systems, linked to at least 13 fatalities (The Guardian

2015). Beyond consumers, exposure risks also affect users indirectly, as shown by the case of Philips, which was criticized for exposing electronics workers to toxic substances, resulting in miscarriages, cancers, and other health impacts (Business & Human Rights Resource Centre 2001).

Finally, the dataset includes *activists and journalists* (5) as victims in the context of corporate operations. Political, environmental and human rights activists, including journalists and media operators, are frequently subjected to harassment and threats, criminalization or violence and in some cases lethal attacks (Glazebrook and Opoku 2018). Their victimization underscores the vulnerability of those attempting to safeguard public interest, transparency, and accountability in contexts where corporate power intersects with weak or complicit governance.

Severity of abuse. We assessed the severity of the abuse using two proxies: (1) whether the abuse involves an abuse of physical integrity, and (2) whether it constitutes a breach of non-derogable norms.

Physical integrity (*Physical integrity* in the BRAVE_v0 database) (1): Drawing on international law and business and human rights literature (Cassese 2012; Donnelly 2013; van der Have 2018), we distinguished between physical and non-physical integrity abuses. This distinction reflects a widely recognized hierarchy in the gravity of rights abuses. *Abuses of physical integrity* (1.a)—such as torture, enforced disappearance, extrajudicial killing, and other forms of violence—are generally considered among the most egregious infringements of fundamental rights (United Nations Human Rights Committee 1992; Donnelly 2013). Such acts violate jus cogens norms, which occupy the highest status in international law (Cassese 2012), and directly undermine the essence of human dignity, an inviolable value at the core of human rights protection (Donnelly 2013).

In contrast, *non-physical integrity abuses* (1.b)—for example, restrictions on freedom of expression, movement, or assembly—though often systematic and serious, typically entail a lower degree of immediate harm to individual integrity (Donnelly 2013). These abuses may erode civic and political freedoms over time, but they do not usually involve direct physical harm.

Abuses of non-derogable norms (Non-derogable right in the BRAVE_v0 database) (2): We further distinguished between abuses involving abuses of *non-derogable (2.a)* and *derogable norms (2.b)*. This classification reflects a foundational principle of international human rights law: certain rights – e.g., the right to life, the prohibition of torture, and freedom from slavery – are defined as *non-derogable*. These rights are absolute and cannot be suspended under any circumstances, including during states of emergency (Bantekas and Oette 2016; United Nations Human Rights Committee 2001). Conversely, derogable rights may be lawfully restricted under narrowly defined and exceptional conditions, such as a declared state of emergency, a threat to national security, or a public health crisis. Even in these cases, any derogation must meet strict requirements: it must be officially proclaimed, necessary and proportionate to the situation, and must not involve discrimination (United Nations 1966). Examples of abuses of derogable rights include abuses of freedom of movement, freedom of assembly, or certain fair trial guarantees.

Table 2 provides the full categorization of abuses according to their severity

TABLE 2 ABOUT HERE

Type of company involvement. In line with the UNGP framework, we distinguished between direct and indirect corporate involvement in human rights and environmental abuses. *Direct involvements (Company direct involvement in the BRAVE_v0 database) (1)* occur where a company – including its parent company or subsidiaries – either causes or contributes to an adverse human rights and environmental impact through its own activities (UNGP 13 (a)). The notion of activities includes both actions and omissions attributable to the company. By contrast, *indirect involvement* or ‘being directly linked’ (2) (*Company indirect involvement*), arises under UNGP 13 (b) when an adverse impact is caused by a third party – including an entity in the company’s global value chain (*Company indirect involvement through GVC*), a local government or government agency (*Company indirect involvement through government agencies*), or other entities such as e.g. armed groups and rebel forces (*Company indirect involvement through other entities*) – but is directly connected to the company’s operations, products, or services through a business relationship (UNGP, Commentary to

Principle 13). Indirect linkage also captures adverse impacts occurring within the sphere of influence of a company – a concept that typically includes the global value chain, where the company may have commercial leverage but lacks direct operational control. In such cases, the company’s legal liability under national laws may be limited or even absent, but the normative accountability under international standards remains applicable.

Table 3 presents qualitative evidence from the coded cases.

TABLE 3 ABOUT HERE

KEY FEATURES OF THE BRAVE DATABASE

In total, we documented 4,314 human rights and environmental abuses involving firms in the sample in the cohort 2000-2020.⁴ Table 4 illustrate some qualitative differences existing between different kinds of human rights abuses, providing concrete examples.

TABLE 4 ABOUT HERE

Overall, the BRAVE dataset finds that 98% of the monitored firms to have at least one reported abusive event during the reference period. Figure 1a reports the annual share of monitored firms with at least one documented human rights or environmental abuse, while Figure 1b displays the total number of codified abuses per year. The share of implicated firms increases sharply over the 2000s, rising from roughly 75% in 2000 to above 90% by the end of the decade. This upward trend persists—with some notable year-to-year volatility—reaching its highest levels around 2016, before gradually declining. A similar pattern emerges in the number of recorded abuses. The total number of abusive events grows steadily throughout the 2000s, peaking at nearly 1,900 cases around 2015, before showing a marked decrease in the final years of the period. Taken together, the two panels indicate a substantial escalation in both the prevalence and intensity of corporate involvement in human rights and environmental abuses during the first decade and a half of the 2000–2020 period.

⁴ For cases in which abuses were reported to begin before 2000, we imputed the starting year as 2000; similarly, for abuses ending after 2020, we imputed the ending year as 2020.

However, from 2015 onwards, both indicators exhibit a downward trajectory, which could reflect improvements in corporate accountability, stronger regulatory and social oversight, or changes in the reporting and documentation of abuses.⁵

FIGURE 1 ABOUT HERE

The codified abuses span approximately 145 countries. Figure 2 illustrates the geographic distribution of these events. The shading reflects the total number of abuses, with darker tones indicating higher counts. The largest shares of reported abuses occurred in Brazil and the United States (6% each), and Nigeria and Colombia (5% each). An additional 248 cases were classified as ‘global’ allegations, reflecting their occurrence worldwide.

*** FIGURE 2 ABOUT HERE***

We also differentiated between abuses taking place in European countries (i.e. EU27 plus the UK, Norway, and Switzerland) and those occurring in the rest of the world. Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of reported business-related human rights and environmental abuses between 2000 and 2020, distinguishing between abuses occurring worldwide, those in Europe, and those outside Europe. The trend of abuses within Europe remains significantly lower, with little variation over time. Overall, the data highlight the importance of taking a geographically differentiated perspective when analyzing business-related human rights and environmental abuses and confirm concerns about the extraterritorial impacts of corporate activities, particularly in contexts where regulatory frameworks are weaker and enforcement mechanisms are limited.

*** FIGURE 3 ABOUT HERE***

As discussed, the BRAVE database includes a wide range of abuses. Table 5 provides a breakdown of human rights and environmental abuses by type and by firms’ level of involvement—either direct or indirect. The most frequently recorded abuses are those related to negative impact on

⁵ Notably, the figure reflects the raw number of codified abuses and does not adjust for potential time trends in the reporting of such events. These trends may be influenced by changes over time in the monitoring and scrutiny of companies.

the environment (1,022 cases, 23.7% of total events) and health (764 cases, 17.7% of the total events), with the majority of these involving direct corporate responsibility. Labor rights abuses also represent a significant portion of the dataset (499 cases, 11.6% of the events), fairly evenly split between direct and indirect involvement. Notably, traditional abuses with more solid legal definitions such as slavery (103, 2.4% of the total events), torture (55, 1.3% of the total events), and trafficking (31, 0.7% of the total events) are also occurring but less frequently, possibly reflecting underreporting, definitional constraints or lower incidence relative to other abuses. The relatively low numbers for actions like the production/export of weapons (11, 0.3% of the cases) and abusive legal actions (10, 0.2% of the cases) may suggest that such events are less commonly reported.

TABLE 5 ABOUT HERE

Figure 4 shows the share of firms involved in at least one abuse (Figure 4a) and the number of abusive events (Figure 4b), by year and type of corporate involvement. The incidence of direct abuses increases steadily throughout the 2000s, peaks around the late 2000s and early 2010s, and subsequently declines after 2015—a pattern that may reflect strengthened compliance systems, enhanced monitoring, or shifts in reporting and enforcement practices. Indirect abuses, while consistently lower in magnitude, follow a similar broad pattern. They increase gradually during the 2000s, reach their highest levels around the early 2010s, and subsequently exhibit a clear downward trend as well. This decline suggests that improvements in oversight and accountability may have also begun to extend—albeit more slowly and unevenly—to firms’ broader supply chains and corporate networks. Further disaggregation of indirect abuses indicates that 56% originate within firms’ global value chains, underscoring how outsourcing and cross-border production networks can diffuse responsibility and weaken oversight. An additional 33% involve collusion or joint involvement with state-related entities, pointing to institutional governance gaps and weak regulatory environments. The remaining 11% concern other third-party actors. Taken together, the evidence highlights the enduring challenge of mitigating human rights and environmental risks beyond the boundaries of the firm, where accountability mechanisms tend to be weaker and more difficult to enforce.

*** FIGURE 4 ABOUT HERE***

Regarding the severity of human rights and environmental abuses, Table 6 reports the frequency distributions of codified cases involving non-derogable abuses and physical integrity abuses. Over the observation period, 83% of the firms in the dataset were involved in at least one non-derogable abuse, while an even higher share (i.e., 89%) was involved in at least one physical integrity abuse. These high values demonstrate that such abuses are not isolated or exceptional, but rather systemic across a broad range of firms, cutting across industries and geographies. In absolute terms, physical integrity abuses account for 1,771 cases (41% of all documented abuses) while non-derogable abuses account for 857 cases, corresponding to 20% of the total. The distribution across victim categories reveals important patterns. In both abuse types, the majority of cases target workers (38% for non-derogable, 45% for physical integrity), followed by abuses against communities (36% and 25%, respectively). Notably, abuses against children are more prominent among non-derogable abuses (14%) than in physical integrity cases (9%). Although less frequent, abuses against consumers and clients (2% and 5%, respectively), and activists and journalists (10% and 6%, respectively) are also present in both categories, indicating the broad reach of harmful corporate conduct.

TABLE 6 ABOUT HERE

USER GUIDANCE AND DATA LIMITATIONS

The BRAVE database follows the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) protocol in accordance with Horizon Europe rules. The database is openly accessible through this link: <https://rebalanceproject.org/data/>. The first released version of the database is indicated as BRAVE_v0. This article serves as the primary reference and codebook of the database. To support the appropriate use and interpretation of the BRAVE data, we outline the principal limitations of the database below. We strongly encourage scholars to take these considerations into serious account when employing BRAVE for empirical analysis.

Firstly, like all datasets built from publicly available allegations, BRAVE data reflect what has been observed and reported by seemingly reliable sources. By their nature, the collection of these kinds of data is inevitably subject to both *false negatives* (abuses that occurred but were never reported or detected) and *false positives* (allegations that, despite careful scrutiny, may still misrepresent the underlying events) cases. While our protocol relies on a high-quality and credible principal source (i.e., BHRRC) and applies systematic manual validation through additional secondary sources, these safeguards cannot fully eliminate measurement error. For this reason, users—particularly those employing the dataset in econometric analyses—should apply appropriate caution and transparency regarding these intrinsic limitations. Moreover, given the impossibility of validating the reliability of companies’ responses to the allegations,⁶ such responses were not included in the BRAVE database.

Secondly, we note that reporting biases such as the ones discussed above are inherent to any media- and CSO/NGO-based dataset – including widely used ESG data. The likelihood that an abuse becomes publicly documented varies across firms, sectors, and countries (Fiaschi et al. 2020). Firms that attract more public scrutiny—because of their size, visibility, or earlier controversial activities—are also more likely to have allegations reported, which may inflate their level of misconduct relative to firms that operate under lower public attention (Fiaschi et al. 2020). When using the dataset for empirical analyses, it is therefore advisable to control for firm-level exposure to scrutiny (e.g., firm size, media visibility, sector, or presence in high-salience controversies), as these factors may correlate with the probability of an additional abuse being reported.

Thirdly, monitoring intensity differs substantially across countries, due to variation in media freedom, civil society capacity, access to information, and the presence of international NGOs or investigative journalists. Countries with stronger monitoring infrastructures or higher international attention are more likely to allow the reporting of abusive events, while abuses occurring in remote

⁶ The BHRRC allows companies to respond to allegations (see <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/from-us/company-response-mechanism/>). The BRAVE database does not include this information. Scholars interested in company responses may wish to complement our data with such information prior to use.

or politically restrictive contexts may remain undocumented (Fiaschi, Giuliani, and Nieri 2017; Surroca, Tribo, and Zahra 2013). This geographic heterogeneity in observability does not necessarily correspond to actual differences in the underlying incidence of abuses and should therefore be accounted for in cross-country analyses—for example by including control variables of media freedom, civil society strength, or country-level reporting capacity.

Lastly, while the BHRRC’s methodology helps exclude unfounded claims and enhances the reliability of reported allegations, it remains susceptible to asymmetries arising from the availability and quality of underlying sources. Importantly, resource constraints meant that the BHRRC expanded its network of country experts gradually. These new experts were not tasked with retrospectively collecting data on incidents predating their involvement. Consequently, reporting of abusive events may exhibit a temporal trend, reflecting both media coverage and the recent proliferation of social media. For these reasons, we recommend accounting for time trends in empirical analyses.

Taken together, these limitations indicate that the dataset should be understood as capturing the universe of observable and credibly documented allegations, within the constraints of the public information ecosystem. Scholars using the data—especially in quantitative analyses—should therefore (i) explicitly consider the potential for under- and over-representation, (ii) incorporate controls for differential visibility across firms and geographies, and (iii) avoid treating the absence of observed allegations as evidence of the absence of corporate misconduct.

AVENUES FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

BRAVE offers new open access data to study corporate human rights and environmental misbehavior. While its evidence may usefully inform advocacy and civil-society interventions, its primary purpose is to enable rigorous academic research and to support evidence-based public policy design. In this respect, BRAVE addresses longstanding limitations in the BHR literature—most notably the paucity of systematic, comparable, and longitudinal data (Ruggie 2013; Deva and Birchall 2020), the difficulty of attributing responsibility within complex global value chains (Locke 2013), and the

scarcity of quantitative analyses capable of testing propositions that have largely remained conceptual or based on studies with limited external validity (Nieri and Giuliani 2018; Fiaschi et al. 2020). By making visible patterns of alleged abuses across firms, industries, geographies, and time, BRAVE opens multiple research agendas that advance beyond the state of the art. We discuss below potential avenues for further research for which the data we have developed may be employed.

Regulatory Efficacy Revisited: Do Human Rights Norms Change Corporate Behavior? A first promising avenue concerns the impact of regulatory developments—both soft law, such as the UNGPs, and hard law, such as mandatory human rights due diligence statutes—on firms’ propensity to be associated with abuses. While difficulties in constructing credible counterfactuals remain, the dataset’s coverage offers the possibility to compare heterogeneous firms’ responses to regulatory shifts and to evaluate which normative innovations meaningfully reduce misconduct. Such analyses would contribute to longstanding debates on the effectiveness of transnational governance regimes in this camp.

The Anatomy of Self-Regulation: When Do Internal Codes and Certifications Work? A second research stream concerns the efficacy of internal codes of conduct, human rights policies, and socio-environmental certifications. Current evidence is mixed and often hampered by self-selection, symbolic adoption, or lack of performance data (Carlos and Lewis 2018), BRAVE makes it possible to test whether these internal commitments correlate with reduced misbehavior, to identify conditions under which they are substantive rather than ceremonial, and to uncover mechanisms—organizational, cultural, or managerial—that determine their effectiveness.

The Economic Payoff Question: Are Abuses Profitable? A third agenda—of particular interest to scholars seeking to establish a “business case for human rights” (Baumann-Pauly and Trabelsi 2021)—involves examining the association between human rights/environmental misbehavior and financial outcomes such as profitability, cost of capital, or competitiveness. Existing empirical work is inconclusive (Cuervo-Cazurra, Purkayastha, and Ramaswamy 2023), partly due to limited abuse-level data. BRAVE allows researchers to test a variety of profitability-related ques

including e.g. whether firms benefit economically from violations, whether markets penalize misconduct, and how these effects vary across industries and institutional environments.

Networks of Influence: Peer Effects, Social Pressure, and Organizational Fields. The dataset's breadth also enables analyses of peer effects and field-level dynamics. Companies embedded in shared sustainability initiatives, or collaborating through co-marketing or supply-chain partnerships may converge in their commitments—or violations—through isomorphic or other kinds of conformity pressures (DiMaggio and Powell 1983). This allows scholars to assess whether peer behavior encourages firms to curb abuses, exacerbates race-to-the-bottom dynamics, or operates differently across governance contexts.

Direct vs. Indirect Abuses: Offloading, Externalization, and Value-Chain Complexity. Another unresolved issue concerns the locus of wrongdoing. Firms may be directly responsible for abuses or may offload harmful practices to suppliers, subsidiaries, or contractors, especially in developing countries characterized by weak labor and environmental protections (Locke 2013). BRAVE allows for comparative examination of direct versus indirect abuses, enabling studies of substitution, displacement, or externalization strategies—phenomena that have been theorized or observed through case-based research, but rarely measured at a larger scale.

Multinational Structures: Subsidiary Autonomy, Integration, and the Geography of Misbehavior. International business scholarship has long theorized how multinational organizational architectures shape strategic responses (Birkinshaw and Morrison 1995; Kostova, Roth, and Dacin 2008), yet empirical work linking these features to human rights outcomes remains sparse. By matching BRAVE data with international business data, it will be possible to perform analyses of how subsidiary autonomy, integration, local responsiveness, and internal control systems relate to different types of abuses, including their diversity, recurrence, or escalation.

Ownership, Finance, and the Governance of Misconduct. Corporate governance is another field where evidence remains largely anecdotal. Little is known about how ownership structures, investor time horizons, and financialization pressures affect misconduct (Jain and Zaman 2020;

Aguilera, Desender, and LopezPuertas-Lamy 2025). BRAVE data can be used in combination with firm-level ownership and financial data, and this enables exploration of how these macro-organizational characteristics generate rights-related or environmental harm, opening the door to a more granular corporate governance outlook on human rights and environmental wrongdoing.

The Human Factor: CEOs, Emotions, Ideologies, and TMT Dynamics. Upper echelons research (Hambrick and Mason 1984) has illuminated how executive characteristics shape firm outcomes, yet scarcely touches on human rights issues. If coupled with CEO data, available by a variety of databases or secondary sources, scholars can exploit BRAVE to investigate how CEOs' values, emotional dispositions, political ideologies, and top management team dynamics affect the likelihood or severity of abuses. This represents an entirely new direction in the behavioral study of corporate misconduct.

Towards a Dynamic Theory of Corporate Human Rights Misbehavior. Ultimately, BRAVE has potential to support analyses that can contribute to the development of a dynamic, empirically grounded theory of human rights and environmental misbehavior—one that integrates regulatory forces, organizational structures, market incentives, peer influences, governance systems, and managerial agency. By enabling multi-level, longitudinal, and cross-national analyses, BRAVE provides the empirical foundations for cumulative theory-building in a field that has historically lacked systematic data.

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TABLES

Table 1. Monitored Companies by Country of Origin

Country	Number of firms
Austria	1
Belgium	1
Denmark	1
Finland	1
France	20
Germany	14
Ireland	4
Italy	4
Luxembourg	1
Netherlands	4
Norway	1
Spain	3
Sweden	2
Switzerland	6
United Kingdom	20
Total	83

Table 2. Severity-Based Categorization of Human Rights and Environmental Abuses

	Physical Integrity Abuses	Non-Physical Integrity Abuses
Non-Derogable Abuses	Arbitrary arrest Child labor Deprivation of life Human trafficking Rape and sexual abuse Slavery Torture Violence	State occupation
Derogable Abuses	Forced relocation of local communities Harassment Health-related harm Injuries at protest Labor exploitation Non-fatal workplace issues Unsafe products for consumers	Abusive legal actions Complicity with other actors Corruption Discrimination Illegal dismissal Infringement of privacy Insufficient/inadequate consultation of local communities and workers Intimidation Land grabbing Negative impacts on cultural heritage Negative impacts on environment Negative impacts on livelihood Political repression Precarious/unsuitable living conditions Production and trade of weapons Recruitment fees Restricted access to food, medicines, water Restriction/repression of freedom of association and/or expression Tax avoidance and evasion Trafficking (other than human)

Note: For some types of abuses i.e., complicity, displacement, labor rights abuses, negative impacts on health, restrictions, trafficking, and violence and harassment, the table reports sub-types. This is because these types of abuses assume different values along at least one of the two severity dimensions, namely whether they involve an abuse of physical integrity and/or a breach of non-derogable norms.

Table 3. Human Rights and Environmental Abuses Classification: Some Examples

	Non-Derogable Rights Abuses	Derogable Rights Abuses	Physical Integrity Abuses	Non-Physical Integrity Abuses
Direct	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of forced labor - Workplace fatalities due to poor health and safety measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Abuse of the workers' freedom of association - Heavy exploitation of natural resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Displacement of indigenous communities due to mining activities - Injuries at work due to poor safety measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dismissal of workers - Denying employees of permanent contracts
Indirect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supplying a government with weapons that are used to carry out mass killings - Sourcing from suppliers that use child labor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sourcing from suppliers that pay their workers a wage that is below the living wage level - Sourcing from suppliers that deny their workers permanent contracts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financing armed groups that threaten activists opposing mining projects - Financing paramilitary groups responsible for the disappearance of community members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financially supporting governments involved in illicit trade of weapons with other countries - Sourcing from suppliers which exploit workers through the practice of debt bondage

Table 4. Qualitative Evidence on Different Types of Human Rights and Environmental Abuses

	Case	Country	Year(s)
<i>Non-derogable Human Rights Abuses</i>			
Direct	The batteries used in their products by companies such as Renault are linked to child labor	DR Congo	2010-2015
Indirect	Evidence of labor exploitation are found in Nestlé’s global supply chain linked to the fish industry	Thailand	2000-2016
<i>Derogable Human Rights Abuses</i>			
Direct	Volkswagen is accused of gender discrimination in access to employment	Spain	2009-2015
Indirect	Local communities opposing extractive activities by Holcim are subject to intimidation by local groups	El Salvador	2000-2015
<i>Physical Integrity Abuses</i>			
Direct	An employee of Veolia is fatally injured in an explosion at a chemical processing center	Canada	2014
Indirect	Fiat Chrysler sources cobalt from the DRC where miners suffer from chronic illness due to prolonged exposure to dust	DR Congo	2011-2020
<i>Non-physical Integrity Abuses</i>			
Direct	Alstom is fined for bribery and corruption	Italy	2000-2006
Indirect	Workers at Nokia’s suppliers accuse the companies of massive lay offs	India	2015

Table 5. Number of Human Rights and Environmental Abuses, per Type and Company**Involvement**

Type of Abuse	Num of Abuses (share)	Num of direct Abuses (share)	Num of indirect Abuses (share)
Abusive legal action	10 (0.2%)	8 (0.3%)	2 (0.1%)
Child labor	84 (2%)	7 (0.3%)	77 (4.4%)
Complicity	54 (1.2%)	0 (0%)	54 (3.1%)
Corruption	113 (2.6%)	100 (3.9%)	13 (0.8%)
Deprivation of life	346 (8%)	147 (5.7%)	199 (11.5%)
Discrimination	200 (4.6%)	158 (6.1%)	42 (2.4%)
Displacement	232 (5.4%)	122 (4.7%)	110 (6.3%)
Intimidation	210 (4.9%)	73 (2.8%)	137 (7.9%)
Labor rights abuses	499 (11.6%)	282 (10.9%)	217 (12.5%)
Negative environmental impact	1022 (23.7%)	809 (31.4%)	213 (12.3%)
Negative health impact	764 (17.7%)	612 (23.8%)	152 (8.8%)
Negative impacts on heritage	26 (0.6%)	24 (0.9%)	2 (0.1%)
Production and trade of weapons	11 (0.3%)	2 (0.1%)	9 (0.5%)
Restriction	263 (6.1%)	106 (4.1%)	157 (9%)
Slavery	103 (2.4%)	12 (0.5%)	91 (5.2%)
Tax avoidance and evasion	60 (1.4%)	56 (2.2%)	4 (0.2%)
Torture	55 (1.3%)	3 (0.1%)	52 (3%)
Trafficking	31 (0.7%)	7 (0.3%)	24 (1.4%)
Violence and harassment	231 (5.3%)	48 (1.9%)	183 (10.5%)
Total	4,314	2,576 (59.7%)	1,738 (40.3%)

Table 6. Frequency of Human Rights and Environmental Abuses by Severity

	Non-derogable Abuses	Physical Integrity Abuses
Num (share) of companies with at least one abuse	69(83%)	74(89%)
Num (share) of abuses	857(20%)	1771(41%)
Num (share) of abuses against workers	326(38%)	802(45%)
Num (share) of abuses against communities	309(36%)	613(35%)
Num (share) of abuses against consumers and clients	17(2%)	94(5%)
Num (share) of abuses against children	120(14%)	165(9%)
Num (share) of abuses against activists and journalists	85(10%)	97(6%)

FIGURES

Figure 1. Share of Firms Involved in Human Rights and Environmental Abuses and Number of Abuses per Year

Source: Authors' own elaboration based on BRAVE_v0 data.

Figure 2. The Geography of Human Rights and Environmental Abuses

Source: Authors' own elaboration based on BRAVE_v0 data.

Figure 3. Number of Human Rights and Environmental Abuses, per Year and Geography

Source: Authors' own elaboration based on BRAVE_v0 data.

Figure 4. Share of Firms Involved in Human Rights and Environmental Abuses and Number of Abuses per Year and Type of Involvement

Source: Authors' own elaboration based on BRAVE_v0 data.

APPENDIX

Appendix A. Detailed Classification of Abuse Types

Type of abuse	Definition	Abuses included
Abusive legal action	Lawsuits or other judicial processes initiated by corporations against people or groups (including human rights defenders and environmental activists) who raise concerns about environmental, social, or human rights impacts of corporate activity (European Union, 2024).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic lawsuits against public participation (SLAPPs).
Child labor	Work that deprives children of their childhood, potential and dignity and is harmful to their physical and mental development. (ILO, 1973, 1999).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employment of child labor within the production and commercialization process.
Complicity	Corporate actions or business relationships indirectly contribute to sustaining unlawful state or non-state practices and human rights abuses (OECD, 2023).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in military occupation; • Partnerships or operations that contribute to the growth or legitimization of illegal settlements; • Involvement in political repression; • Financial, logistical, or operational support to armed groups, paramilitary forces, or state security actors implicated in human rights abuses.
Corruption	Abuse of entrusted power for private gain, through engaging in bribery, kickbacks, favoritism, illicit payments to secure business advantages (UNGA, 2003).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bribery and misuse of funds in international contracts; • Corruption of political elites enabling rights abuses; • Fraudulent dealings involving public officials in relation to project approvals.
Deprivation of life	Corporate involvement in practices, contexts, or omissions that directly or indirectly cause an individual arbitrary deprivation of life (United Nations, 1966).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatal workplace incidents; • Killings of activists and disappearances; • Indirect support to government accused of genocide and mass repression; • Killings of workers during labor disputes.
Discrimination	Differential treatment of individuals or groups based on characteristics or socio-economic status (United Nations, 1996).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hiring and promotion bias; • Unequal pay and benefits; • Precarious and discriminatory contracting; • Pregnancy discrimination.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health-status discrimination.
Displacement	Removal of individuals or communities from their homes or land without free, prior, and informed consent, directly or indirectly caused by business operations (United Nations Economic and Social Council 1998).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land grabbing; • Infrastructure and projects implemented without consultation of local communities; • Displacement of local community due to the development of corporate projects.
Intimidation	Actions or threats intended to coerce, silence, or punish individuals or communities for exercising their rights (United Nations General Assembly 1998).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surveillance of activists and NGOs; • Death threats and violence against community leaders; • Threats against whistleblowers exposing corporate misconduct; • Threats linked to land grabs and forced evictions.
Labor rights abuses	Corporate practices that undermine internationally recognized labor rights and standards (ILO 1981, 1973; United Nations 1966).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unpaid wages and wage arrears; • Exposure to hazardous substances without protection; • Precarious contracting and denial of permanent work; • Unfair dismissals; • Excessive or coercive recruitment fees; • Inadequate on absent consultation with trade unions; • Injuries suffered during protests related to corporate activities; • Non-fatal workplace issues; • Restriction of freedoms (expression and association).
Negative environmental impact	Significant harm, damage, or adverse change to the environment resulting from corporate practices that violate, or risk violating, international obligations related to environmental protection (European Union 2012).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to climate change through emissions; • Pollution of air, water and soil (including oil spills, and toxic waste dumping); • Depletion and exploitation of natural resources; • Loss of biodiversity through deforestation and overfishing; • Insufficient or inadequate consultation with local community on project's impact; • Operations that damage protected ecosystems; • Operations that compromise conservation areas or violate environmental preservation standards.

Negative health impact	Corporate practices that cause adverse impacts on human health and undermine the right to health (United Nations 1966, 2011).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to toxic substances resulting in health-related harms; • Inadequate housing; • Disruption of local livelihoods; • Insufficient consultation of local communities concerning the project health impact; • Restricted access to food, medicines, and water; • Manufacturing and selling unsafe products for consumers.
Negative impacts on heritage	Negative impacts on heritage refer to business activities that damage, appropriate, or weaken tangible and intangible cultural heritage, thereby eroding collective identity, spiritual traditions, and intergenerational bonds to land and history (United Nations 1966; United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization 2003).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destruction, flooding, or alteration of historically or archaeologically significant sites through large-scale projects or extractive operations; • Appropriation, commercialization, or misuse of culturally significant practices, objects, or spaces.
Production and trade of weapons	Corporate involvement in the production, trade, or supply of weapons and dual-use materials that cause indiscriminate harm, violate international humanitarian law, or contribute to nuclear, chemical, or biological weapons program (United Nations 2013).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of cluster munitions and weapons; • Supply of arms to regimes engaged in unlawful repression or conflicts; • Financial support to regimes developing illicit nuclear programs.
Restriction	A limitation placed on sovereign rights or the exercise of individual freedoms (ILO 1948; United Nations 1966).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corporate practices that restrict or suppress freedom of association or expression; • Infringement of privacy; • Involvement in the arrest and detainment of groups and individuals by state forces.
Slavery	Condition in which individuals are treated as property and deprived of their freedom (ILO 1930).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forced labor; • Debt bondage; • Coercive recruitment practices.
Tax avoidance and evasion	Corporate practices aimed at unlawfully or unethically minimizing tax obligations, undermining states' fiscal capacity (OECD 2012).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of tax havens subsidiaries; • Deliberate misclassification and misdeclaration of information to avoid paying taxes; • Profit shifting to low-tax jurisdictions.

Torture	The intentional infliction of severe physical or mental pain or suffering for purposes such as information extraction, punishment, intimidation, coercion, or discrimination, when carried out by or with the consent of state authorities (United Nations 1984).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in torture and ill-treatment of protestors, political opponents, human rights defenders and environmental activists by state and non-state entities.
Trafficking	Illegal trafficking in persons: any act of recruitment, transport, harboring, or receipt of individuals by coercive or deceptive means for exploitation (United Nations 2000).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in human trafficking for the purpose of exploitation; • Illegal trade or smuggling of goods, including tobacco, drugs and arms.
Violence and harassment	Corporate practices (including acts or threats) that cause physical, sexual, psychological, or economic harm, intimidation, or distress, targeting an individual or group, and which interfere with the enjoyment of fundamental human rights or occupational rights (United Nations 1966).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harassment and bullying by companies to retaliate against union representatives for their activities; • Physical injuries during protests; • Involvement in violent acts by state forces and non-state actors against opponents of corporate activities; • Sexual harassment in the workplace. • Rape and sexual abuse.